

Simultaneous analysis of the intestinal parasites and diet through eDNA metabarcoding

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Abstract

Agricultural expansion and intensification are having a huge impact on plant and arthropod diversity and abundance, affecting food availability for farmland birds. Difficult food access, in turn, can lead to immunosuppression and a higher incidence of parasites. In the studies designed to examine changes in the diet of birds and their parasites, metabarcoding is proving particularly useful. This technique requires mini-barcodes capable of amplifying the DNA of target organisms from fecal environmental DNA. To help to understand the impact of agricultural expansion on biodiversity, this study sought to design and identify mini-barcodes that might simultaneously assess diet and intestinal parasites from the feces of farmland birds. The capacity to identify diet and parasites of 2 existing and 3 newly developed mini-barcodes was tested “in silico” in relation to the behavior of a reference eukaryotic barcode. Among the newly designed mini-barcodes, MiniB18S_81 showed the higher taxonomic coverage of eukaryotic taxa and a greater amplification and identification capacity for diet and parasite taxa. Moreover, when it was tested on fecal samples from 5 different steppe bird species, MiniB18S_81 showed high taxonomic resolution of the most relevant diet and parasite phyla, Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa at the order level. Thus, the mini-barcode developed emerges as an excellent tool to simultaneously provide detailed information regarding the diet and parasites of birds, essential for conservation and management.

Key words: biomonitoring, broad-spectrum primers, eukaryotic mini-barcodes, fecal eDNA, farmland birds, parasitology

INTRODUCTION

Owing to the ever-changing climate and land use patterns, biodiversity is increasingly under threat (Pimm

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et al. 1995; Jetz *et al.* 2007). In the last 50 years, especially, agricultural expansion has brought about changes in land use that have severely compromised biodiversity (Meyer & Turner 1992; Matson *et al.* 1997; Pain & Pienkowski 1997; Newton 1998; Chamberlain *et al.* 2000; Benton *et al.* 2003). Among other consequences, the expansion of croplands is diminishing plant species abundance and richness (Wilson *et al.* 1999; Storkey *et al.* 2012; Fonderflick *et al.* 2020), which ultimately affect both the seed banks (Wilson *et al.* 1999; Andreasen *et al.*

2018) and the seasonality of seed availability (Newton 2004). Furthermore, as the seeds used in intensive agriculture are mostly treated with pesticides, this has devastating repercussions on the birds that ingest these seeds (Prosser & Hart 2005; Lopez-Antia *et al.* 2015; Millot *et al.* 2017; Eng *et al.* 2019). The intensification of agriculture has also been identified as the main driver of the decline of insect populations (Benton *et al.* 2002), which is another important dietary component of many bird species, and their declines are already having a notable impact on insectivorous bird communities (Bowler *et al.* 2019). Land use changes and reduced food availability are stress factors for birds, affecting their health and immune response (Kitaysky *et al.* 1999, 2007; Hoi-Leitner *et al.* 2001; Pigeon *et al.* 2013; Almasi *et al.* 2015) by lowering their defenses against parasites (Korschgen *et al.* 1978; Wakelin 1996; Nordling *et al.* 1998). Synergistic effects of food availability, parasitism, and stress have been observed on bird population densities (Chapman *et al.* 2006). Disease/parasitism and nutrition often interact to determine the abundance of wildlife populations. Helminthic and protozoan parasites can directly impact host survival and reproduction through pathological effects and indirectly by compromising the host's health state (Coop & Holmes 1996; Murray *et al.* 1998). Hence, parasitism is also an important factor to consider as a potential risk for both wild and farmland bird species (Lafferty 1997; Dunn *et al.* 2014; Stockdale *et al.* 2015; Cabodevilla *et al.* 2020).

To date, the studies designed to address the diet of farmland birds have paid most attention to available trophic resources (plants and arthropods), without confirming whether these were consumed or not (Salamolard & Moreau 1999; Holland *et al.* 2006, 2012; Faria *et al.* 2012), whereas the studies focusing on the ingested prey have examined the diet through visual identification of the remains of prey exoskeletons present in the feces of the birds (Jiguet 2002; Browne *et al.* 2006; Holland *et al.* 2006; Bravo *et al.* 2017). Despite this identification method being widely used for diet analysis, it does not generally go beyond the ordinal taxonomic level and few individuals are identified at deeper levels (Jiguet 2002; Browne *et al.* 2006; Bravo *et al.* 2017). In addition, some of the ingested preys could remain undetected or unidentified because of the difficulties in identifying them after undergoing digestion (Moreby 1988; Pompanon *et al.* 2012). The case of parasitological studies conducted in farmland birds is similar as most have involved the visual identification of parasites (Browne *et al.* 2006; Okulewicz & Sitko 2012; Rengifo-Herrera *et al.* 2014; Presswell & Lagrue 2016) often via the dissection of dead animals

(Villanúa *et al.* 2008; Santoro *et al.* 2010; Okulewicz & Sitko 2012). However, in non-invasive studies of fecal samples, the most abundant parasites can be visually identified although low intensity parasitism is hardly discernible (Rengifo-Herrera *et al.* 2014; Presswell & Lagrue 2016). Moreover, taxonomic identification based on the morphological appearance of the eggs of many species is also limited or even impossible (Browne *et al.* 2006; Presswell & Lagrue 2016).

The introduction 20 years ago of environmental DNA (hereafter eDNA) analysis opened a new avenue for ecology (Taberlet *et al.* 2012b). This method has quickly gained importance in parallel with high-throughput sequencing technology (Shokralla *et al.* 2012; Taberlet *et al.* 2012a,b) and is becoming increasingly popular for the study of diet, microbes, and parasites (Pompanon *et al.* 2012; Shokralla *et al.* 2012; Taberlet *et al.* 2012a; Bass *et al.* 2015; Kerley *et al.* 2018). Through eDNA analysis, relevant information can be obtained from non-invasive samples such as feces (Srivathsan *et al.* 2016), thus avoiding the need to examine dead animals. The use of this technique on fecal samples allows to investigate the host genetics, parasites, gut microbiota, and diet (Srivathsan *et al.* 2016). In addition, although metabarcoding cannot be considered a quantitative tool, several studies have shown some quantitative capacity of this method (Evans *et al.* 2016; Lamb *et al.* 2019; Piñol *et al.* 2019). Accordingly, it should be possible to compare the proportions of each taxon among similar samples, for example, water samples from different ponds or feces collected in different seasons (Pompanon *et al.* 2012).

Many different barcodes (usually longer than 300 bp) have been designed for DNA metabarcoding, both specific and broad-spectrum (Prosser *et al.* 2013; Hadziavdic *et al.* 2014; Van Steenkiste *et al.* 2015; Cheng *et al.* 2016; Krehenwinkel *et al.* 2018). Nevertheless, the length of the barcode used in environmental metabarcoding studies should be carefully chosen (Deagle *et al.* 2006, 2007; Hajibabaei *et al.* 2006; Taberlet *et al.* 2012b) because the DNA from water, soil, air, or feces is often degraded (Deagle *et al.* 2006; Yu *et al.* 2012; Taberlet *et al.* 2012a). Studies that have focused on the metabarcoding of eukaryotic eDNA have already described specific mini-barcodes (shorter than 300 bp) for different taxa (Epp *et al.* 2012; Pompanon *et al.* 2012), although they provide a narrow view of the sample. On the contrary, broad-spectrum mini-barcodes can provide information on both target taxa and on their overall contribution to a higher category taxon, allowing to get a better understanding of the sample. Thus, the use of proper broad-spectrum mini-barcodes may allow to get relevant information on diet

and intestinal parasites in the same analysis. However, as far as we know, the eukaryotic mini-barcodes available have not been tested with this purpose in mind.

The use of candidate mini-barcodes to identify taxa, nevertheless, depends on the existence of a robust reference sequence data (Clarke *et al.* 2014). Moreover, for an accurate estimate of biodiversity, a sufficiently variable DNA region needs to be amplified. The most used DNA genes for barcode design are mitochondrial cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit 1 (COI) and cytochrome *b* (cytb) and nuclear 12S rRNA, 16S rRNA, and 18S rRNA gene sequences together with internal transcribed spacer regions 1 and 2 (i.e. ITS1 and ITS2) and ribulose biphosphate carboxylase large chain (rbcL) (Hajibabaei *et al.* 2007; Pompanon *et al.* 2012; Andújar *et al.* 2018; Djurhuus *et al.* 2020). The barcodes designed for these genes have been widely used for analysis of environmental samples in a wide range of taxa including mammals, birds, and invertebrates. Among these, the 18S rRNA gene spans an especially variable region for which there exists a robust and constantly expanding reference dataset (Hadziavdic *et al.* 2014).

The main goal of this study was to identify an appropriate mini-barcode for eDNA analysis on fecal samples to retrieve information on both the diet and the intestinal parasites of birds. We assessed already existing mini-barcodes as well as self-designed mini-barcodes targeting the 18S or 28S rRNA genes in terms of their suitability for use on bird fecal samples. Once we had identified a candidate mini-barcode, it was tested empirically using a high throughput sequencing approach on fecal samples of different steppe bird species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mini-barcode design

We used a dataset of 5000 sequences (species) selected randomly from SILVA SSU v132 reference and non-redundant database (Quast *et al.* 2013), downloaded via the function *obisilva* of OBITools software (Boyer *et al.* 2016). The selection process was based on sequence annotation of the SILVA database including sequences of 1000 species for each phylum Phragmoplastophyta, Apicomplexa, Arthropoda, Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes. The sequences were then aligned in Geneious software v11.1.4 (Biomatters Ltd, New Zealand; Kearse *et al.* 2012) and the resulting alignment formed the baseline for the design of the primers. Primer design was performed using Geneious software v11.1.4.

with the following parameters: primer length 18–27 nucleotides, melting temperature (T_m) 57–63°C, and GC content 30–80%. Next, we assessed mini-barcodes for their potential to form dimers or alternative amplicons. Two approaches were implemented: (i) 100 mini-barcodes (amplicon size < 200 bp) were designed to cover the sequences of Nematoda and Platyhelminthes phyla (2000 sequences; Table S1, Supporting Information); and (ii) 20 mini-barcodes (amplicon size 100–200 bp) were designed using the full dataset of 5000 sequences (Table S2, Supporting Information). Mini-barcodes were then selected according to the following criteria:

1. Mini-barcodes appearing in both approaches.
2. Mini-barcodes covering a variable region (V1 to V9) of the 18S rRNA gene.
3. Mini-barcodes covering the edge of the alignment area were discarded as in this region there was no information for many sequences.
4. In the case of mini-barcodes generated with similar primers, we selected the longer mini-barcode.

After this filtering, 3 mini-barcodes were selected, 2 for the V3 region (MiniB18S_41 and MiniB18S_43) and 1 for the V7–V8 region (MiniB18S_81) (Table 1).

Mini-barcode test on real tissue

We first tested whether the designed mini-barcodes (Table 1) could amplify DNA in simple PCRs conducted on 7 tissue samples of 6 different phyla: a nematode (*Ascaridia galli* Schrank, 1788), a cestode (*Railletina cestitillus* Molin, 1858), an insect (*Apis mellifera* Linnaeus, 1758), an arachnid (*Ischyropsalis pyrenaea* Simon, 1872), a leech [*Helobdella stagnalis* (Linnaeus, 1758)], a gastropod [*Cepaea hortensis* (O. F. Müller, 1774)], and a bird (*Scolopax rusticola* Linnaeus, 1758). DNA extraction from tissues was performed using the kit DNeasy® Blood & Tissue Kit (Ref. 69 506) (QIAGEN). All PCR reactions were carried out using 1 μ L of DNA in reactions with 1.25 μ L of MgCl₂ (25 mM), 2 μ L of dNTPs (20 mM), 2.5 μ L of 10 \times Buffer B, 0.3 μ L of each forward (20 pM) and reverse (20 pM) primers, 1 μ L of BSA (10 mg/mL), and 0.25 μ L of BIOTAQ™ DNA Polymerase of Bioline (ref. BIO-21 060; 5 U/ μ L). The thermocycle conditions were: 96°C for 1 min and 35 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 57°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 1 min. PCR amplification capacity was confirmed by electrophoresis in 1.5% TBE agarose gel. All tested barcodes showed capacity to amplify the DNA of these 7 different tissue samples belonging to 6 different phyla (Nematoda, Cestoda, Annelida, Mollusca, Arthropoda, and Vertebrata).

Table 1 List of barcodes tested in this study

Barcode	Primer	Mean length	Reference
MiniB18S_41	F: CAGGGTTCGATTCCGGAGAG R: CACCAGACTTGCCCTCCAAT	156 bp (mini-barcode)	This study
MiniB18S_43	F: AACGGCTACCACATCCAAGG R: CACCAGACTTGCCCTCCAAT	125 bp (mini-barcode)	This study
MiniB18S_81	F: GGCCGTTCTTAGTTGGTGGA R: CCCGGACATCTAAGGGCATC	150 bp (mini-barcode)	This study
566F/1200R	566F: CAGCAGCCGCGGTAATTCC 1200R: CCCGTGTTGAGTCAAATTAAGC	610 bp (large-barcode)	Hadziavdic <i>et al.</i> 2014
nucLSUDf1/nucLSUDr1	nucLSUDf1: CGTCTTGAAACACGGACCAAG nucLSUDr1: GCATAGTTCACCATCTTTCGGG	156 bp (mini-barcode)	Sonnenberg <i>et al.</i> 2007
Short28SF/ Short28SR	Short28SF: GTGTAACAACCTCACCTGCCG Short28SR: GCTACTACCACCAAGATCTG	154 bp (mini-barcode)	Vestheim and Jarman 2008

More information on amplicon lengths is provided as Fig. S2, Supporting Information.

“In silico” PCR

We also checked by “in silico” PCR the new mini-barcodes (Table 1) together with the 2 eukaryotic mini-barcodes of the 28S rRNA gene most widely used in next generation sequencing (NGS) diet studies (Pompanon *et al.* 2012): nucLSUDf1/nucLSUDr1 (Sonnenberg *et al.* 2007) and Short28SF/Short28SR (Vestheim & Jarman 2008). In addition, we compared the taxonomic coverage and resolution of these mini-barcodes to those of the reference eukaryotic barcode F566/R1200 (Hadziavdic *et al.* 2014) (Table 1). This barcode has been identified as the best eukaryotic barcode among “de novo” designed and previously existing universal eukaryotic 18S rRNA barcodes (Hadziavdic *et al.* 2014).

All mini-barcodes were tested “in silico” using the program ecoPCR (Ficetola *et al.* 2010) and OBITools (Boyer *et al.* 2016). First, we used the *obisilva* function to download the ecoPCR format SILVA 132 SSU reference (cleaned to keep only high quality sequences) and non-redundant dataset. Likewise, we downloaded the ecoPCR format SILVA 132 LSU reference dataset. SILVA does not have a non-redundant version of the 132 LSU dataset, so when interpreting the results of the coverage and taxonomic resolution at the species level, it should be taken into account that there may be some repeated species in the database. Second, we used the function *ecotaxstat* of ecoPCR (Ficetola *et al.* 2010) to test the taxonomic coverage of the 3 designed mini-barcodes, F566/R1200 eukaryotic long barcode (650 bp), and nucLSUDf1/nucLSUDr1 and Short28SF/Short28SR 28S mini-

barcodes on Bacteria, Archaea, and Eukarya. In the same way, we used the functions *ecotaxstat* and *ecotaxspecificity* to test their taxonomic coverage and resolution capacity on 10 eukaryotic phyla (Table S3, Supporting Information): Apicomplexa, Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes, including main parasites of birds; Phragmoplastophyta, Annelida, Arthropoda, and Mollusca which may appear in birds’ diets; Ascomycota and Basidiomycota to check for fungal sample contamination; and Vertebrata to check if the barcodes could identify the host. We especially focused on the phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Apicomplexa, Arthropoda, Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes, as we anticipated these would be the taxa mostly represented in the diet and parasites of birds. The *ecotaxspecificity* option *-e 0* was used, which does not allow any mismatches. Taxonomic classification was assigned according to SILVA’s reference database (www.arb-silva.de).

Case study using field-collected samples

Finally, based on both the taxonomic coverage and the resolution capacities revealed in the “in silico” PCRs, we selected the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode for the assessment in a real metabarcoding analysis. The samples tested were fecal samples from 12 bird flocks of 5 different steppe bird species; 1 flock of farmed red-legged partridges (*Alectoris rufa* Linnaeus, 1758), 2 flocks of wild red-legged partridges (*Alectoris rufa* Linnaeus, 1758), 4 flocks of pin-tailed sandgrouse (*Pterocles alchata* Linnaeus, 1766), 1 flock of black-bellied

sandgrouse (*Pterocles orientalis* Linnaeus, 1758), 2 flocks of great bustards (*Otis tarda* Linnaeus, 1758), and 2 flocks of little bustards (*Tetrax tetrax* Linnaeus, 1758). All the samples were collected between 2016 and 2017 in the province of Ciudad Real (Spain) with the exception of the samples of a pin-tailed sandgrouse flock collected in 2017 in the province of Lleida (Spain).

Feces were collected in the roosts without trapping any birds and, whenever possible, fresh feces from 20 individuals of each flock were collected. DNA extractions were performed using the QIAamp® DNA Stool Mini Kit from QIAGEN (Ref. 51 504); 15 to 20 DNA samples were obtained per flock (DNA could not be extracted from every sample). The concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) and quality (A260/280 and A260/230 ratios) of each DNA sample were measured using the NanoVue Plus spectrophotometer (GE Healthcare). Samples from each flock were mixed according to DNA quantity and quality in 3 pools of 5 to 7 samples, 1 of high, 1 of medium, and 1 of low quantity (Fig. S1, Supporting Information). Subsequently, DNA was amplified using PCR from extracts using each of the designed primers (miniB18S_81F and miniB18S_81R) (Table 1) at the Analytical Services (SGIker) of the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU). To retrieve enough amplified DNA for the sequencing reaction, 3 PCR reactions were run per sample pool. We included blanks within the library construction and negative controls were sequenced. We did not detect any contamination, neither in the PCR product nor in the sequencing output. Samples were purified and a second reaction was performed to index each amplified product and attach Illumina adaptors using the Illumina Nextera v2 kit. We used the same Illumina adaptor for the 3 pools prepared for each flock. Amplification was carried out using 1 μL of DNA in a reaction mix containing 1.25 μL of MgCl_2 (25 mM), 2 μL of dNTPs (20 mM), 2.5 μL of 10 \times Buffer B, 0.3 μL of each forward (20 pM) and reverse (20 pM) primer, 1 μL of BSA (10 mg/mL), and 0.25 μL of GoTaq® Flexi DNA Polymerase from Promega (ref. M829; 5 U/ μL). The thermocycle conditions were: 96°C for 1 min and 35 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 57°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 1 min. Once amplified, PCR outputs were sequenced in an Illumina MiSeq NGS platform (sequencing of 2 \times 150 bp paired-end reads) with the MiSeq Reagent Kit v2, following the manufacturer's instructions.

The bioinformatic analyses of the sequencing output were conducted using the Cutadapt (Martin 2011) and Usearch (Edgar 2010) software packages. First, the adapters were cut and the forward and reverse sequences combined. We used the *join.fastq* function of Usearch in-

stead of merging forward and reverse sequences to avoid losing sequences of amplicons longer than 300 bp. The sequences were then cleaned (*fastq_filter* function of Usearch), the unique sequences and OTUs were identified using *fastx_uniques* and *cluster_otus* functions of Usearch respectively, and OTU table was built based on 97% OTUs using the *usearch_global* function. Subsequently, the *syntax* function of Usearch was used to predict the taxonomy of the OTUs obtained with a *cutoff* of 0.8 and a combined 18S and 16S dataset. The reference dataset was built combining the SILVA 18S v123 dataset (Quast *et al.* 2013) with the RDP 16S v16 training set (Cole *et al.* 2014), both provided by the Usearch platform. We opted for the RDP 16S v16 training dataset instead of a complete SILVA, Greengenes or RDP 16S dataset because of the high level of mistaken sequences reported for these datasets (Edgar 2018).

All the graphs were constructed using the *ggplot2* package (Wickham 2016) in R v3.6.1 (R Core Team 2019).

RESULTS

“In silico” testing

All the tested mini-barcodes showed short mean amplicon lengths (Table 1), and each of the mini-barcodes displayed very little variation in the amplicon length (Fig. S2, Supporting Information). Although the 5 mini-barcodes generated amplicons between 30 and 900 bp, percentages of sequences longer than 300 bp were negligible (0.06% MiniB18S_41, 0.05% MiniB18S_43, 1.16% MiniB18S_81, 0.34% nucLSUDf1/nucLSUDr1, and 0.32% Short28SF/Short28SR). In the case of MiniB18S_81, cestodes showed larger amplicons with a mean length of 299 bp.

Based on “in silico” amplifications, both the 5 mini-barcodes and the reference eukaryotic barcode showed high taxonomic coverage for the eukaryotic organisms and null capacity to amplify organisms of the taxa Bacteria and Archaea (Fig. 1). Of the 3 mini-barcodes designed in this study, MiniB18S_81 showed the highest taxonomic coverage for eukaryotic organisms. This mini-barcode showed the capacity to amplify the 91.1% of the eukaryotic species' sequences present in the SILVA reference database, which is the highest score obtained among the mini-barcodes tested in this study. Only the large barcode 566F/1200R showed a slightly better taxonomic coverage for eukaryotic organisms (92.6%; Fig. 1). In addition, all barcodes showed a good capacity to amplify eukaryotic phyla sequences: MiniB18S_41 showed

Figure 1 “In silico” taxonomic coverage capacity of barcodes of Bacteria, Archaea, and Eukarya taxa. Grey color represents the proportion of amplified species and black color the proportion of non-amplified species. Inside of each graph is the percentage of amplified species and below the graph is the number of amplified species upon total species of these taxa in reference data set.

the capacity to amplify species of 131 out of the 138 phyla in the SSU reference database (i.e. the 94.9% of the phyla), MiniB18S_43 showed the capacity to amplify 129 out of the 138 phyla (93.5%), MiniB18S_81 showed the capacity to amplify 132 out of the 138 phyla (95.7%), 566F/1200R showed the capacity to amplify 136 out of the 138 phyla (98.6%), nuLSUDf1/nuLSUDr1 showed the capacity to amplify species of 85 of the 88 phyla in the LSU reference database (96.6%), and Short28SF/Short28SR showed the capacity to amplify 85 of the 88 phyla (96.6%).

All barcodes were able to amplify large numbers of organisms of the 10 target phyla (Table S3, Supporting Information). However, MiniB18S_81 was able to amplify more than 90% of the species of 7 of these 10 phyla and showed the best taxonomic coverage among the mini-barcode tested, as good as the taxonomic coverage of the large barcode 566F/1200R (Table S3, Supporting Information). Within the existing 28S mini-barcode, nuLSUDf1/nuLSUDr1 showed the poorest taxonomic coverage of several phyla, amplifying less than 80% of the species of 5 out of the 10 phyla examined (Table S3). MiniB18S_43 and nuLSUDf1/nuLSUDr1 mini-barcode showed the worst capacity to detect species of the phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Arthropoda, Nematoda,

Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa (Fig. 2). The former did not provide a high taxonomic coverage for Nematodes and the latter behaved poorly on all the taxa, especially for Nematoda and Apicomplexa (Fig. 2). The MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode provided the best results, showing an excellent taxonomic coverage on Arthropoda, Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes, despite a slightly lower taxonomic coverage for the Apicomplexa phylum than MiniB18S_41, MiniB18S_43, and Short28SF/Short28SR (Fig. 2). Finally, all the 5 mini-barcode and reference 566F/1200R barcode displayed a high taxonomic coverage for the Fungi kingdom and its phyla Ascomycota and Basidiomycota (Table S3, Supporting Information).

The taxonomic resolution of the large barcode 566F/1200R was higher than any of the mini-barcode (Table 2; Table S3, Supporting Information). Nevertheless, the resolution capacity of the 5 mini-barcode was high, and MiniB18S_81 showed the best resolution for the phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa (Table 2). In fact, this mini-barcode offered high taxonomic resolution at the order level within the phyla Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa; at the family level in Platyhelminthes and Apicomplexa; at the genus level in Apicomplexa; and at the species level in Arthropoda,

Table 2 “In silico” resolution capacity (in percentage) of barcodes for phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa, represented as the proportion of unambiguously identified classes, orders, families, genera, and species within each phylum

	MimiB18S_41	MimiB18S_43	MimiB18S_81	566F/1200R	nucLSUDfI/ nucLSUDrI	Short28SF/ Short28SR
Arthropoda						
Class	71.4 (10 of 14)	69.2 (9 of 13)	76.9 (10 of 13)	85.7 (12 of 14)	100 (11 of 11)	90.9 (10 of 11)
Order	52.6 (40 of 76)	50 (38 of 76)	73 (54 of 74)	89.5 (68 of 76)	100 (4 of 4)	100 (4 of 4)
Species	21.1 (2623 of 12445)	19.5 (2434 of 12489)	59.2 (7451 of 12591)	76.8 (9752 of 12700)	62.4 (2835 of 4542)	52.9 (2626 of 4960)
Phragmoplastophyta						
Class	33.3 (1 of 3)	33.3 (1 of 3)	100 (3 of 3)	100 (3 of 3)		
Order	8.6 (10 of 117)	8.6 (10 of 117)	31.2 (37 of 119)	80.3 (94 of 117)		
Genus	18.6 (336 of 1804)	17.0 (307 of 1808)	39.4 (706 of 1791)	87.3 (1531 of 1753)		
Species	29.4 (2265 of 7709)	28.3 (2254 of 7975)	34.5 (2676 of 7756)	65.9 (5013 of 7609)	29.7 (2391 of 8061)	31.7 (2820 of 8884)
Nematoda						
Class	100 (2 of 2)	100 (2 of 2)	100 (2 of 2)	0 (0 of 2)	100 (2 of 2)	100 (2 of 2)
Order	26.67 (4 of 15)	20 (3 of 15)	53.3 (8 of 15)	80 (12 of 15)	60 (3 of 5)	60 (3 of 5)
Species	47.5 (932 of 1961)	46.6 (727 of 1560)	61.6 (1270 of 2062)	86.4 (1811 of 2095)	58.7 (229 of 390)	33.3 (197 of 591)
Platyhelminthes						
Class	100 (6 of 6)	100 (5 of 5)	100 (5 of 5)			
Order	79.5 (31 of 39)	71 (27 of 38)	89.7 (35 of 39)	94.9 (37 of 39)	100 (8 of 8)	100 (8 of 8)
Family	86.11 (31 of 36)	83.8 (31 of 37)	100 (37 of 37)	100 (37 of 37)		
Species	52.2 (900 of 1723)	49.3 (837 of 1699)	81.5 (1523 of 1869)	92.9 (1567 of 1687)	33.1 (174 of 526)	30.7 (182 of 593)
Apicomplexa						
Class	100 (4 of 4)	100 (2 of 2)	100 (2 of 2)			
Order	100 (5 of 5)	100 (4 of 4)	100 (5 of 5)			
Family	100 (5 of 5)					
Genus	76.2 (48 of 63)	73.8 (45 of 61)	70.97 (44 of 62)	96.9 (63 of 65)	81.8 (9 of 11)	83.3 (10 of 12)
Species	34.03 (487 of 1431)	31.6 (453 of 1435)	41.3 (526 of 1274)	76 (1122 of 1477)	34.7 (43 of 124)	36 (85 of 236)

Resolution percentages are shown only for the taxonomy categories for which there were sufficient data available. The number of unambiguously identified taxa among the total number of taxa available for each taxonomic category in the reference dataset is shown in brackets. To see all the taxonomic resolution results, go to Table S3, Supporting Information.

Figure 2 “In silico” taxonomic coverage of barcodes of the phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa, represented as the proportion of amplified species. For all results of taxonomic coverage, go to Table S3, Supporting Information.

Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes. However, no results were obtained at the family and genus levels for various phyla, as this information was lacking in the reference dataset (Table 2).

Case study using field-collected samples

The MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode provided a coverage of more than 100 000 reads per sample and high-quality sequences, with an average of 66% of forward/reverse combined sequences showing less than one expected error (others were discarded). Moreover, on average, 80.4% of reads were assigned to an OTU with 97% identity. Taking as a reference both the SILVA 18S v123 dataset and RDP 16S v16 training dataset, the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode identified 1367 of 1384 OTUs recovered as eukaryotic organisms with certainty, whereas no sequences were assigned to Bacteria or Archaea.

Our metabarcoding analysis results were also consistent with the data obtained through “in silico” PCR. The MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode showed an excellent taxo-

mic resolution capacity at the order level for Apicomplexa, Arthropoda, Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes, while for plants it only showed good resolution at the class level (Table 3). In the Apicomplexa phylum, this mini-barcode also offered good resolution capacity at the family and genus levels (Table 3). However, no results were obtained at the family and genus levels for various phyla, probably due to the lack of information in the reference dataset regarding these taxonomic levels and phyla (Table 3). We did not include the Annelida and Mollusca phyla in Table 3, as only 2 OTUs of each were detected in this analysis. MiniB18S_81 also showed good taxonomic resolution at the class level in Ascomycota and Basidiomycota (Table 3). In contrast, the taxonomic resolution for the Vertebrata phylum was poor, which is in line with the results of the “in silico” approach. In addition, this mini-barcode was capable of unambiguously identifying some genera. Among these, we should highlight *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *Blastocystis* spp., 2 groups of microorganisms of increasing interest due to their impact on human health.

Table 3 Resolution capacity (in percentage) of the mini-barcode MiniB18S for different taxa according to the metabarcoding test, represented as the proportion of sequences unambiguously identified at the level of phylum, class, order, family, genus, and species

MiniB18S_81		Taxonomic resolution					
Kingdom	Phylum	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
Alveolata		82.9	75	71.1	55.3	39.5	5.3
	Apicomplexa		81.3	81.3	62.5	62.5	6.3
Chloroplastida		89.4	84.8	7.1		2.4	4.1
	Phragmoplastophyta		93.2	7.7		2.7	4.6
Fungi		84	59.5	40.5	10.5	10	3
	Ascomycota		67.1	50.6	10.6	9.4	2.4
	Basidiomycota		84.6	48.1	15.4	19.2	5.8
Metazoa		89.0	72.0	63.3	0.5		16.5
	Arthropoda		95.9	84.7			17.3
	Nematoda		100	94.4			44.4
	Platyhelminthes		91.7	83.3	8.3		
	Vertebrata		17.6				8.8

Phragmoplastophyta, Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa are presented in bold. Resolution percentages are shown only for the taxonomy categories for which there was sufficient taxonomic information in the reference dataset. Annelida and Mollusca excluded due to lack of information.

The use of MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode allowed to estimate the percentage of reads for each taxon in relation to the total reads obtained for each sample (Fig. 3), which allowed to estimate the contribution of each taxon to the birds' diet, gut microbiota, or parasite community.

DISCUSSION

Fecal samples are of great value as a non-invasive means to gather information on the feeding ecology and parasite infestation of species, supporting the management and conservation of their populations. This study aimed to identify the best mini-barcode of eukaryote 18S rRNA to be used in studies based on feces metagenomics that could simultaneously analyze the diet and parasites in birds, with special emphasis on threatened farmland birds. Among the mini-barcodes developed in this study, MiniB18S_81 (of gene 18S rRNA) in particular showed a great taxonomic coverage of almost all eukaryotic taxa, as well as a good taxonomic resolution of the most interesting phyla associated with the diet and parasitology of birds (Jiguet 2002; Villanúa *et al.* 2008; Santoro *et al.* 2010; Bravo *et al.* 2017) through both “in silico” and real metabarcoding testing. Thus, the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode is able to provide a highly valuable information for farmland bird conservation.

All the tested mini-barcodes displayed short and homogeneous amplicon lengths, obtaining in general sequences shorter than 300 bp. In the case of MiniB18S_81, the amplicons longer than 300 bp corresponded mainly to the taxonomic group Cestoda, probably related to the insertion of more than 100 bp in the V7–V8 region of the 18S gene. Although the species belonging to this phylum are parasites, DNA of cestodes in feces samples is usually not as degraded as other fecal DNA, since it is extracted directly from tissues (adults, larvae, or eggs). Thus, we strongly believe that this methodological drawback should not be a problem when studying the parasitology on fecal samples. However, in those studies where the identification of cestodes in the sample is essential, an Illumina kit that provides sequencing reads of 300 bp should be used.

The variability of the V7–V8 region of the 18S gene was not totally unexpected, since this region is much more variable than the V3 region (Hadziavdic *et al.* 2014). In fact, this seems to be the reason why the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode has a higher taxonomic coverage and resolution capacity than the MiniB18S_41 and the MiniB18S_43 mini-barcodes. When we compared the features of the newly-designed MiniB18S_81 with 2 of the eukaryotic mini-barcodes most widely used in NGS diet studies, it proved to be slightly superior to the Short28SF/Short28SR 28S mini-barcode (Vestheim &

Figure 3 Mean percentages of reads of phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Arthropoda, Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa by bird species.

Jarman 2008) in terms of the taxonomic coverage for 4 out of the 5 target phyla.

Overall, both MiniB18S_81 and the Short28SF/Short28SR mini-barcodes showed a broad taxonomic coverage and resolution for all examined phyla. However, the available reference datasets for LSU (the DNA region amplified by the Short28SF/Short28SR mini-barcode) are not as long as those for SSU (the DNA region amplified by the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode) and could contain redundant sequences, and without a robust reference database, information is lost (Clarke *et al.* 2014). Likewise, the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode showed a much wider taxonomic coverage than the 28S mini-barcode nucLSUdf1/nucLSUdr1 (Sonnenberg *et al.* 2007), which indeed, among the tested mini-barcodes, proved to be the most inefficient tool for eDNA analysis of diet and parasites on bird fecal samples.

In the metabarcoding test conducted on feces of different steppe bird species, MiniB18S_81 proved to have a great taxonomic resolution capacity at the order level of the targeted phyla, especially in the case of Apicomplexa, Arthropoda, Nematoda, and Platyhelminthes, where more than 80% of the obtained OTUs were unambiguously

identified at order level. With regards to the Phragmoplastophyta, the taxonomic resolution at class level provided a representation of the importance of plants in the birds' diet. Hence, the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode provides information on the contribution to the bird's diet of different arthropod orders, other invertebrates, and plants, as well as information about the bird's parasites, at least at the order level. The lower taxonomic resolution observed at species level in the metabarcoding test is likely attributable to the fact that many of the OTUs recovered corresponded to organisms that were not included in the reference dataset, and thus it does not allow to assess the real resolution capacity of the mini-barcode at this level. Although the percentage of reads obtained for each taxa cannot be considered quantitative of the real contribution of these taxa to the gut microbiota (Evans *et al.* 2016; Lamb *et al.* 2019; Piñol *et al.* 2019), this percentage could be useful for comparative studies (Cabodevilla *et al.* 2021). However, it should be noted that this is a representation and not a quantification and that we do not know the behavior of this mini-barcode with respect to plants and animals. In the future, the affinity of this mini-barcode for the different taxa should be tested using mock samples.

The capacity of MiniB18S_81 to unambiguously identify some pathogens such as the genera *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *Blastocystis* spp. suggests its possible use for estimating parasite loads. In effect, there is much interest in *Blastocystis* spp. because of their impacts on human health (Tan 2008; Scanlan 2012) and zoonotic capacity (Greige *et al.* 2018). This parasite has proved to be far more common in wildlife than previously considered, due to the limitations of previous diagnostic techniques and the lack of surveillance in wildlife (Parkar *et al.* 2007). It was long considered to be of no clinical significance, but there is growing consensus that these parasites can have major impact on host health and thus influence population survival and reproduction (Thompson *et al.* 2010). Studies of *Blastocystis* spp. have often been based on the presence/absence of OTUs, and this new mini-barcode could provide information on the proportions of this organism in the host's gut microbiota especially useful for comparative studies. This will help to determine the prevalence of these gut parasites in the population over time, as well as to assess the potential impact of *Blastocystis* spp. on wildlife health.

Both “in silico” and real metabarcoding testing also showed that MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode displays good taxonomic coverage for the phyla Ascomycota and Basidiomycota. This is particularly crucial when working with eDNA, as environmental contamination with fungi could be a problem (Bohmann *et al.* 2014). By using this broad-spectrum mini-barcode proposed here, fungal contamination can be detected and contaminated samples discarded.

In conclusion, the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode is a promising new tool for simultaneous biomonitoring of diet and intestinal parasites through eDNA metabarcoding of fecal samples. It provides useful information about the arthropod orders and plants in the diet, as well as about the contributions of Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, and Apicomplexa parasites to the gut microbiota. Understanding the ecological determinants of animal density is a central question in the field of species conservation, especially if we consider the current rate of human interference. In this context, the MiniB18S_81 mini-barcode could provide a better insight into the ecology of farmland birds and help to elucidate the reasons for their population decline.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of the article.

Table S1 List of mini-barcodes designed based on 2000 Nematoda and Platyhelminthes DNA sequences

Table S2 List of mini-barcodes designed based on the full dataset of 5000 DNA sequences: 1000 sequences per phylum (Phragmoplastophyta, Apicomplexa, Arthropoda, Nematoda and Platyhelminthes)

Table S3 Taxonomic coverage and resolution at different taxonomic levels (in percentage) of each primer pair across the 10 target phyla and their respective kingdoms

Figure S1 Diagram of the sample processing, from fecal samples to sequencing in an Illumina MiSeq NGS platform.

Figure S2 Amplicon lengths in each barcode.